

Evaluating the Current Asylum System for Climate Refugees and Recommendations to Create a Global Policy:

Abstract:

This article critically examines the drawbacks of current policies and frameworks addressing asylum applications for climate refugees. It proposes a four-phase policy approach, with concrete timelines and commentary on the potential advantages and challenges of its implementation. The article also introduces a model that incorporates economic and social indicators, using ND-GAIN and socio-economic weights to predict patterns in climate migration and assess the countries that will contribute to and accept climate refugees. By integrating principles of international refugee law, historical policy responses to refugee distribution, and modern data analysis, the article offers a phased legal pathway for future policy development on environmental migration.

Introduction:

Climate change has already displaced nearly 376 million people since 2008. As the frequency of extreme climate like floods, storms and sea levels get worse, the numbers will keep rising. Without a clear system to handle displaced people, it becomes imperative to devise a framework for handling these refugees.¹ These so-called ‘climate refugees’ can be classified into two main categories: 1) Migrants who have left their homes as a result of extreme climate; and 2) Migrants fleeing their homelands due to rising sea levels. Current asylum and immigration processes do not give such migrants any guarantees of expedited citizenship or resident status, often treating them like ordinary applicants for citizenship or permanent residency status. This article hopes to shed light on this issue, covering problems in the existing framework as well as mentioning developments that have taken place towards the inclusion of these migrants in existing refugee frameworks. In criticising the present framework, recommendations to improve the system have been put forth to address the gaps in the policy. It is also important to mention that in recognising internal displacement caused as a result of climate change, this article primarily deals with trans-national migration by persons displaced due to extreme weather events and other such related events.

While climate refugees are a global problem affecting every single region of the world, there can be certain trends that can be observed in climate migration. Based on existing patterns, the tendency is for people to migrate from regions of high risk to regions of low risk. Using the University of Notre Dame’s study on the vulnerability of countries, it is clear that countries with lower incomes and in certain geographical zones, such as Oceania and Sub-Saharan Africa, are at greater risk of climate change-related events such as rising sea levels and drought and people living in these regions will move to safer countries in the same region or to a completely different region.² Countries at the receiving end of this climate migration have not seen the pressing need for a policy to deal with these refugees, but if estimates of 1.2 billion people becoming displaced by climate change become true, then a concrete policy will

have to be formulated that does not only place the burden of supporting these refugees on a few countries but also on all regions that have not been impacted.³

Evaluating Current Frameworks for Climate Refugees:

The UNHCR defines a refugee as someone who “is outside his or her country of nationality or habitual residence; has a well-founded fear of persecution because of his or her race, religion, nationality, membership in a particular social group, or political opinion; and is unable or unwilling to avail himself or herself of the protection of that country, or to return there, for fear of persecution.”⁴ Therefore, under the present framework, migrants who are fleeing the effects of climate change are not classified as refugees, and no country is forced to offer them benefits that they would normally offer refugees. These benefits include the obligations of countries to offer protection and citizenship to these displaced persons and grant them the same freedoms and rights given to natural citizens of that particular nation. This trend is best exemplified in the court case, *Ioane Teitiota v. The Chief Executive of the Ministry of Business, Innovation, and Employment in New Zealand*. The Teitiota family had illegally migrated from Kiribati, citing climate change as the cause for appealing for refugee status, but the Supreme Court of New Zealand held that they did not come under the scope of the Refugee Convention.⁵

While there is a lot to be done to ensure the rights of climate migrants, this is not to say no developments have been made in addressing the issue. The New York Declaration adopted by the United Nations General Assembly recognises how climate or environmental change can cause migration, and it is accepted that it was an influential first step towards creating a concrete policy. The declaration’s other objectives included reducing pressure on host countries and increasing refugee self-reliance, crucial steps towards creating a sustainable global refugee policy.⁶ The Global Compact on Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration in 2018 stated, as part of its objectives, [to] strengthen joint analysis and sharing of information to better map, understand, predict, and address migration movements, such as those that may result from sudden-onset and slow-onset natural disasters, the adverse effects of climate change, environmental degradation, as well as other precarious situations, while ensuring effective respect for, protection, and fulfilment of the human rights of all migrants.⁷

One of the more successful programs was The Nansen Initiative, launched by the Swiss and Norwegian governments in 2012. Its aim is to address this issue by creating a consultative body to help countries and the world at large devise a framework for handling displacement due to climate disasters.⁸ Apart from the Nansen Initiative, the African Union adopted the Kampala Convention, which states all member states must amend or create laws within their respective countries to provide shelter to people who have been internally displaced within Africa due to, among other reasons, natural disasters.⁹

The United Nations General Assembly passed a resolution that recognised an individual’s right to an environment with a safe climate as a basic human right, which represents the relation between the environment and human rights, thus underscoring the need to ensure climate migrants’ access to this basic right by developing a framework to rehabilitate these migrants in the so-called “climate safe zone.”¹⁰ This requires a global action plan and not the effort of a single body or country. Moreover, a lot of the legislation that exists is primarily focused on giving refuge to victims of natural disasters like cyclones or droughts instead of global climatic phenomena like rising sea levels or the thawing of the Arctic. The first step

will be to redefine refugees to encompass climate refugees and to counter the legal hurdles that come with this policy move. Further, adding to the challenge is the expedited timeline for creating this legal basis in the face of growing climate risks.

Recommendations to Create a Comprehensive Climate Refugee Framework:

In creating a framework for transnational climate migrants, it is important to create a pipeline for the implementation of this policy and define the recurrent key terms involved in the formulation of this policy. In this context, a climate-safe zone can be defined as a region or regions that are either not frequently prone to climatic disasters and climatic phenomena or that have developed resistance to such climatic events. The proposed pipeline for the formulation of this framework involves the following steps: 1) Creating a formal and widely accepted definition for the term environmental refugee; 2) determining the rights and protections for such environmental refugees; 3) developing a system for the efficient redistribution of climate refugees; and 4) combating issues that might arise in the rehabilitation of refugees in the host countries. Also, it is worth mentioning that this article proposes a framework that isn't all-encompassing and provides just the basic idea for dealing with this multifaceted issue.

Coming to the history of climate refugees, the term environmental refugee was first defined by Essam El-Hinnawi, a UNEP expert, in 1985 as “those people who have been forced to leave their traditional habitat, temporarily or permanently, because of marked environmental disruption (natural and/or triggered by people) that jeopardised their existence and/or seriously affected the quality of their life.¹¹” While this definition does cover most climate refugees who may be forced to migrate, the term “seriously affected” is ambiguous and difficult to quantify. Therefore, it is necessary to clarify that if the change in climate economically affects the lives of a person or persons, they do not qualify as environmental refugees because, in this case, the number of refugees will be too large. If a person’s source of livelihood has been lost due to the changing climate, the onus is on the national government to generate new employment opportunities. It is also important to note that a person will be classified as a climate refugee only if the climate changes to such a great degree, such as in the event of a loss of occupation or shelter, that it makes it impossible for them to stay in that region. As this article primarily deals with trans-border migration as a result of climate change, climate refugees can be defined as “persons from a particular region at high risk of climate disruption who have been forced to migrate to another country because conditions in their own region make it impossible for them to live.” It is also important to clearly differentiate climate refugees from people who have chosen to migrate to another country voluntarily, even when they could migrate to a safe place within their own country. In differentiating between a climate migrant and refugee, it is useful to look at the internationally accepted definition of a refugee and the rights granted to them. However, in considering the difference between a climate refugee and another type of refugee, there are certain privileges that this paper advocates against.

Refugees have the right to claim asylum in a host country without being deported except under exceptional circumstances, and they have the right to be treated as citizens of that particular nation. However, in the case of climate refugees, it would be unfeasible to offer them the same protections. In the case of climate refugees, the right to non-refoulement should

not be given, except under certain circumstances. To reduce pressure on other countries, it is important to clarify that refugees must first try to seek refuge in safe regions within the borders of their own country, and a host country should be given the right to deport persons who have sought refuge in that host country when there are areas in that person's native country that are in large part safe from the effects of climate change. For example, people from parts of the island of Java cannot claim asylum in Australia, citing the changing climate as a cause when they live in regions such as Central Kalimantan, where there is less risk of sinking and where the frequency of climate events is lower. The exception that can be made to this clause is in cases where regions that are climatically safe zones happen to have other threats to human life, such as conflict, armed insurgency, or crime. For example, in Nigeria, the south is threatened by climate disasters while there are terrorist groups in the north. So, in all cases, internal migration should be preferred over intra-country migration to ensure that the global community doesn't suffer from refugee fatigue. If a refugee does meet all the criteria for coming under the category of a climate refugee, in that case, similar to other refugees, they must be given guarantees of basic human rights in their host countries, like freedom of movement, religion, assembly, etc. Such a definition reduces the number of refugees that need to be dealt with while at the same time giving everyone the opportunity to save themselves from the wrath of climate change-related events.

After a person from an area of high climate risk claims asylum in a country, there should be an international system to process the application and give citizenship to the refugee instead of the national processes that exist today. Unlike conventional refugees, who have to show proof of persecution, these climate refugees will just need to show proof that they are citizens of a region or country that has been internationally deemed unsafe to live in based on meteorological factors. Once the initial processing is done by an independent international organisation, there should be a system for determining how many refugees a safe country can take in without adding too much burden to that country's resources. The aforementioned body will also act as an international delimitation committee that looks at factors such as geographical size, economic ability, law and order, existing population, government policy, etc. of the safe zone to create a formula for the even distribution of refugees. This will ensure no country or region will be unfairly burdened with an excess number of refugees just by virtue of being located close to an area that is at high risk from climate change. It will also be the duty of this international organisation to arrange for means of transport for the refugees from the country they claim climate asylum to the country where they are given. Once a climate refugee receives citizenship, there must be guarantees put in place to ensure that they receive all the basic human rights and benefits that a citizen of that country receives. There must also be a mechanism to ensure that people with certain disabilities or in need of particular care are assigned to countries where the government gives its citizens these benefits. Recognising that all countries do not offer the same benefits to their citizens and forcing refugees to go to a particular safe zone based on a system they have no control over is fundamentally unfair; therefore, climate refugees will be offered another method of citizenship under the proposed framework. If a climate refugee does not want to go to a country assigned to them, they can alternatively apply for a temporary international passport, like the Nansen Passport, which existed in the aftermath of World War I.¹² Such a passport will give them the right to freely move within countries that are signatories to the proposed framework and will also give them the right to work in these countries. After being issued these passports, refugees can earn money in the country of their choice and proceed to attain regular citizenship using existing processes in the country of their choice. In addition to these mechanisms, countries that do not want to take in as many refugees as prescribed by the international body for domestic reasons should be bound by the organisation to provide

economic aid for supporting these refugees to countries receiving them. In enacting such a provision, this should not be a way for countries to get away with not taking in refugees, which would be detrimental to the very idea of sharing refugees. Such measures, along with limits placed on who falls under the category of climate migrants, should make countries in general more receptive to the idea of enacting such a framework.

The map given below represents possible routes of migration and distribution taken by climate migrants to flee from the areas of highest climate risk. The heatmap is based on the University of Notre Dame's ND-GAIN score. The thickness of the lines indicates the number of climate refugees; therefore, the map shows that there is a large number of people fleeing from the Pacific Islands to Australia and being re-distributed from there to South America and Northern Asia. There are also patterns of migration from the Sahel region of Africa to Europe, where they are being re-distributed to North America and Asia. Further, a model using the ND-GAIN score, population, population density, and GDP per capita, assigning greater weight to the ND-GAIN score and equal weightage to population density and GDP per capita, indicates that there are 8 main countries that are likely to be feeders for such refugees and 57 countries that can possibly take in refugees. Based on this model, the total number of refugees could be as high as 30 million people, who can be easily distributed among the 57 countries. While this model may not be completely accurate as it is based on rough weights and does not account for refugees and climatic risk factors in some countries in Oceania and Central Africa, there is reason to believe that the rough trends brought out by the model are likely to happen in the future.

Figure 1: Climate Refugee Flow: The thickness of the lines represents the probable flow volumes

The thickness of lines in the above model is roughly determined using a first-order differential equation for estimating the number of refugees that a country may receive. The variables impacting the volume of refugees can be divided into constant variables and variables that change as a function of time. Constant factors are distance from feeder country, determined using the previous weighting analysis, Porosity of the border, taking into account security and geographical considerations, and immigration policies more generally. Variation in the ND-GAIN Score and refugee sentiment are variable over time and likely to have a strong relationship with the volume of refugees. While, the proposed model does aim to prevent adverse impacts of changing refugee sentiment and immigration policy on climate

refugees, decisions to arrive at a particular country are still likely to be influenced by these factors at least in the short run. The equation given below models these relationships:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = k \cdot \left(\frac{P.I}{D} \right) \cdot (c(t) + s(t))$$

$\frac{dR}{dt}$ represents the change in the number of refugees over time

k is a proportionality constant

$\left(\frac{P.I}{D} \right)$ Static influence on the target variable

$c(t) + s(t)$ Variable effect on the target variable, comprising refugee sentiment and variation in climate risk.

A combination of these two models optimized for a particular country should act as broadly accurate interpretation for the initial flow as well as the later transport of excess climate refugees to ensure their equitable distribution per the proposed measure.

Even if the proposed framework ensures that national governments do not discriminate against refugees, there is bound to be some discrimination from society as a result of deeply steeped historic perceptions about refugees. While there is some reason to believe that these refugees won't be subject to this sort of discrimination because of a sense of guilt in the populace, especially in the west, which makes them feel that they are responsible for the plight of these climate refugees, there are sure to be some factions of society that do not share this sentiment. To combat these issues, society will have to be educated about the economic benefits of refugees, and governments should take steps to ensure adequate refugee representation in political institutions. Strict punishments will have to be imposed on people and organisations committing hate crimes or discriminating against refugees. A financial incentive, provided by historic polluters, could also be given to countries that provide asylums to a certain number of climate refugees, which could further help counteract the negative outlook of such refugees.

The timeline envisioned for the implementation of the above-mentioned targets is around 20–25 years. The issue of climate migrants is not very big in the present, but it is bound to become a big issue in the near future if we don't develop a plan to deal with it. Beyond these initiatives, it is also necessary to develop a system in which governments volunteer to evacuate affected persons from their native lands in the aftermath of a climate disaster and then process them as climate refugees. In doing so, we shall be dealing with the issue of climate refugees proactively instead of resorting to reactive mechanisms, which are outlined in this article. Further, the process of refugees migrating from their native lands to areas where they can claim asylum is often dangerous and involves them walking for several miles or taking boats. Efforts should be made in the long term to ensure that refugees do not have to resort to such unsafe means to get to intermediary safe areas.

While the set of solutions proposed in the essay can solve the issue in part, it is worth considering some problems that might arise in the implementation of these policies. Firstly, there is no world standard for determining climate risk; therefore, such an agreement will also have to include a section that adopts one particular indicator as the primary determinant of

climate risk. Secondly, the process of redistribution proposed can be more complicated as refugee considerations such as the need for education, healthcare, etc. are to be taken into account; determining this is a subjective matter, and metrics will have to be established to determine this. A lot of these concerns are at the implementation phase of the policy, which this paper does not focus on. The historical and quantitative explanation given, justifies the potential of the policy framework, however, more specific analysis is needed to determine the most optimal way to implement this.

Conclusion:

As the world slowly progresses towards a future where climate disasters will become more common and entire sovereign countries will be wiped off the world map or be uninhabitable, it is essential that the global community devise a system to deal with the victims of climate change. This urgency is best highlighted in the President of Tuvalu's speech from knee-deep water in COP 26 when he said, "We are sinking, but so is everyone else. We cannot wait for speeches when the sea is rising all around us at the same time."¹³ In providing a solution for the problem of climate migrants, this article provides a two-pronged approach of limiting the number of people who classify as climate refugees and redistributing the refugees among the various safe zones of the world. While this article also does not delve too deeply into the nitty-gritties of executing such a plan or convincing the global community to accept such a plan, instead aims to provide an overview of a methodology of dealing with climate refugees in the future. International Policy-based action has a reputation of being slow and ineffective but, there is reason to believe that world leaders will act and create a framework along these lines, as they did in the aftermath of World War II to create the United Nations. Problems in the past were faced by a particular geographical region or country, but this is possibly the first time in history that mankind at large is facing an issue of such great magnitude that it threatens to disturb life on our planet. Therefore, we will have to be united in our response, and protect the most vulnerable people, climate refugees, and this will be a testament to our collective action.

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⁴ UNHCR - The UN Refugee Agency. "Convention and Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees | UNHCR." *UNHCR*, www.unhcr.org/media/convention-and-protocol-relating-status-refugees.

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⁷ *GLOBAL COMPACT FOR SAFE, ORDERLY AND REGULAR MIGRATION*. 11 June 2018, refugeesmigrants.un.org/sites/default/files/180711_final_draft_0.pdf.

⁸ Nansen Initiative | Department of Economic and Social Affairs. 17 Dec. 2021, sdgs.un.org/partnerships/nansen-initiative.

⁹ “African Union Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons in Africa (Kampala Convention).” *African Union Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons in Africa (Kampala Convention)*, 2009, au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/36846-treaty-kampala_convention.pdf.

¹⁰ United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), et al. “What is the Right to a Healthy Environment?” *Information Note*, 2022, www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/2023-01/UNDP-UNEP-UNHCHR-What-is-the-Right-to-a-Healthy-Environment.pdf.

¹¹ Apap, Joanna and European Parliamentary Research Service. “The concept of ‘climate refugee’: Towards a possible definition.” *EPRS | European Parliamentary Research Service*, 2019, [www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2018/621893/EPRS_BRI\(2018\)621893_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2018/621893/EPRS_BRI(2018)621893_EN.pdf).

¹² Vinke, Kira. “The Freedom to Move in Response to Uninhabitability: Enabling Climate Migration by a Nansen-Type Passport.” *The Pontifical Academy of Sciences*, no. 152, pp. 229–41. www.pas.va/content/dam/casinapioiv/pas/pdf-volumi/scripta-varia/sv152pas.pdf#page=230.

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